

8th ICSD 2022 Conference

Abstract

Cyprus boasts some of the darkest night skies in Europe, excellent weather conditions, clear skies for most of the year, and an optimal geographic location, making it ideal for astronomical observations and thus the development of relevant tourism activities. To date, very little has been done on the island to develop this niche tourism market, despite its potential to significantly diversify Cyprus's tourism offering, which is largely based on the 'sun and sea' model, and to minimise the strong unsustainable seasonality that the island's tourism industry is facing. Observing this gap, organisations in Cyprus in the fields of education, research, technology, astronomy, tourism, and sustainability came together to develop a new tourism product, Astrotourism. The objective was to develop attractive Astrotourism products in a sustainable manner. To do this, the team focused on researching and evaluating best practices and existing international Astrotourism products, assessing their advantages and disadvantages, and adapting them to the local situation so that they could be implemented in a way that would produce environmental, economic, social, as well as cultural benefits for Cyprus. This resulted in the development of a sustainability framework for the implementation of three Astrotourism activities: Astrocamp, Astropark, and Astrovillage. The framework takes a holistic view of the activities ranging from their location to their set-up and equipment, and to resource consumption and waste management. This sustainability framework was applied and tested during the first pilot implementation of the newly developed products in March and April 2022, through evaluations undertaken by the participants and observations done by the research team. The results indicate that the sustainability framework is effective as it increased the sustainability of the Astrotourism activities, improved the experience of the participants, and raised awareness about sustainability.

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